

OpenWebSearch.eu

“Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search Infrastructure to Support Europe’s Digital Sovereignty”

Deliverable D3.4
The OpenWebSearch Hub and the
Open Web Index Y2

Version 1.0

Open Web Search

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Preliminaries

i. Project Info

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ii. Project Partners

Acronym	Partner
UNI PASSAU	University of Passau
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities
RU	Radboud University
WEBIS	Leipzig University
TUGraz	Graz University of Technology
DLR	German Aerospace Center
CERN	CERN
IT4I@VSB	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Associated Partner)
OSF	Open Search Foundation e.V.
A1	A1 Slovenia
SUMA-EV	Suma e.V. (Associated Partner)
CSC	CSC – Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy
NLnet	Stichting NLnet

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iv. Deliverable Summary

This document describes the second version (out of three) of deliverable D3.3 “The OpenWebSearch Hub and the Open Web Index” of the OpenWebSearch.EU project funded by the EC under the GA 101070014 within the Horizon Europe Framework programme. It specifies the current state of the development and deployment of the Open Web Index (OWI) and the OpenWebSearch Engine Hub (OWSE-HUB), as compared to the first year, and discusses the planning for the next (and final) year.

Note that this deliverable is a stand-alone document, an extended and updated version of last year's D3.3 v1.

v. Document Management

History of Changes

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Almost final version	2.3	24.09.2024	Addressed suggestions from review
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vii. Executive Summary

Two important outputs of the project — and the main focus of work package 3 — are the Open Web Index (OWI) and the OpenWebSearch Engine Hub (OWSE-HUB). Our general vision for both these systems are described in the project proposal (Tasks 3.1 and 3.3). In this deliverable, we reiterate this vision in a more concrete way and discuss how a federated data architecture can be set up to help achieve this vision. Instead of discussing only the OWI and OWSE-HUB, this deliverable covers the complete technical pipeline and relevant components that we have developed in the project. This helps to make our progress as transparent as possible and at the same time offers a deeper understanding of the steps we take to crawl the Web and turn these crawls into a usable index.

For the first year, we have put our main focus on the development of a first end-to-end pipeline for building the OWI. In short, this means that WPs 1, 2 and 3 have focused on setting up a basic version of the crawler, preprocessing pipeline and indexer, respectively, with all of these projects running on the infrastructure provided by WP 5.

In the second year, we have iterated on this pipeline, made it more robust, incorporated it in the LEXIS platform, and started running it on an additional data center. We have improved tooling for using the OWI with the development of command line tool `owlix` to *slice and dice* parts of the index easily, for downloading or remote querying. We have also created a UI for MOSAIC (the search application software developed in WP4) to easily set up and deploy custom search engines on top of the OWI.

While the applications on top of the OWI (`owlix` and MOSAIC) are coming along nicely, robust and automated deployment of our pipelines within the LEXIS platform has proven to be more challenging than anticipated. Stabilizing the data pipelines to ensure high throughput and availability of our index datasets is thus our number one priority for the coming months. The other improvement to make is the processing of updates, to ensure we can propagate modifications to data availability, especially important for responding to take-down requests.

In summary, we have achieved the following main contributions:

1. End-to-end pipeline: We have developed a full pipeline to crawl, pre-process and index the Web on a federated data infrastructure, which runs successfully at (at least) one of the infrastructure partners. The output of this pipeline is the Open Web Index. We are working on fully incorporating this pipeline within the LEXIS platform to automate processing of the crawled data and creation of index datasets on a daily basis.
2. Architecture & Infrastructure: The entire setup operates in four cluster tiers, the Crawling Cluster Tier (CCT) for crawling the Web; the Crawler Frontier Tier (CFT) for managing and coordinating the multi-tier crawling process; the Preprocessing and Enrichment Tier (PET) for preprocessing and cleaning of the Web data; and the Indexing and Storage Tier (IST) for indexing and partitioning the data into readily usable index shards.
3. Statistics: As of September 2024, over 300TB has been crawled and a total of over 2B documents has been indexed into almost 200 daily index datasets.
4. Standards: All data outputs are stored and exchanged in well-known, easily usable, standard formats: WARC for crawl outputs; Parquet for metadata stores; and CIFF for indexes.
5. Open-source software: All software developed is published as open-source software packages (see Section 4.1). Archived versions are available on Zenodo.

As part of our ongoing documentation efforts, the contents of this deliverable will be included in the online Open Web Search Book¹.

¹ The Open Web Search Book, <https://openwebsearcheu.pages.it4i.eu/owseu-the-book/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

1. Introduction

This document describes our progress on the Open Web Index (OWI) and the OpenWebSearch Engine Hub (OWSE-HUB) after the first two years of the project. Before we show the technical details of our work, we first explain our vision for the OWI and OWSE-HUB in Sections 1.1 and 1.2. This vision includes a federated data structure spread across Europe (see also Figure 1), where each data center is responsible for crawling a set of web pages and cleaning and indexing them locally. After introducing our vision, we present the full technology stack developed thus far to build and deploy the OWI and OWSE-HUB — from crawling and parsing the Web to indexing and deployment.

Rather than focusing on the end product of our efforts (the OWI and eventually the OWSE-HUB), we choose to highlight all the steps required to successfully gather all data and process it into a usable index. This should result in a clear picture of how we aim to build and deploy the OWI and OWSE-HUB, and allow for more transparency into our current progress in line with WP6 recommendations.

1.1. Vision for the Open Web Index

The Open Web Index (OWI) accommodates a variety of search engines, by making it easy for search engine designers to use (parts of) the index for their own purposes. To this end, we envision the OWI to become a (distributed) information system similar to the well-known Docker hub. Instead of virtual machines, though, the OWI would contain pre-built indexes that would be readily usable. Our general vision for this distributed system is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: General architecture of the OWI, and the way in which a search engine could interact with the OWI to retrieve (parts of) the index.

Our federated data infrastructure (spread across multiple European data centers) crawls, enriches and indexes web content in a distributed manner. These indexes are fragmented into a set of pre-defined (possibly overlapping) verticals, and continuously updated over time. Aside from these vertical indexes, we also create a “core” index that should contain the most popular and important websites on the Web. Since a small subset of the Web accounts for a large amount of user clicks, a core index containing only this popular subset of the Web should suffice for a large number of basic queries.

When taken together, these index “shards” form the OWI enable a number of downstream uses (also shown in the overview above).

1. Users or organisations can download (or “pull”) a specific, pre-built index.
 - a. They can choose a specific timestamp or checkpoint of the index (e.g. “latest” for the most recent version).
 - b. They can choose to download a selection of checkpoints, instead of only a single one (e.g. “all” for the complete history of a specific index).
2. Users or organisations can create (or “build”) their own index locally, using a dataset of their choice (e.g. privacy sensitive data, such as a corporate filesystem, or personal email).
3. Users or organisations can upload (or “push”) a custom index or custom metadata to contribute to the OWI.

The core data structure behind the OWI is the inverted file, a mapping between each term on the Web and the pages or documents in which it appears. To ensure usability of the OWI, we have chosen to store the inverted files in a common, easily transferable format: the Common Index File Format (CIFF)².

CIFF is a Protobuf schema that describes the inverted files in a structured, consistent and minimal format. A CIFF file consists of the following data:

- A header, containing basic statistics about the collection (e.g. the number of documents, the number of unique terms, the average document length, etc.).
- For each term in the corpus, a record with the document frequency (how many documents contain the term), the collection frequency (how often the term occurs in total throughout the collection), and a posting list. The posting list has an entry for each document in which the term appears, containing an internal document identifier and the term frequency (how often the term occurs in that document).
- For each document in the corpus, a record with the internal, numeric document identifier, the external document identifier (allowing the document to be mapped back to the original corpus), and the document length.

The CIFF standard contains the basic information needed to build a successful search engine using an index, which makes it easy for an existing search engine to import the data and transform it to their internal data structures — easier than transforming it from one search engine’s internal format into another’s. In fact, the CIFF standard was proposed by the developers of a number of existing open source search engines (like Lucene³, (Py)Terrier⁴, and PISA⁵), and these search engines already support reading from and/or writing to CIFF. As a result, the indexes we build in the project can readily be used by external parties with minimal extra effort.

As part of our work on and with the OWI, we also investigate limitations of the CIFF standard, and propose extensions of the format where necessary.

² Lin, Jimmy, et al. "Supporting Interoperability Between Open-Source Search Engines with the Common Index File Format". *Proceedings of the 43rd International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*. 2020.

³ Apache Software Foundation (2000). Lucene, <https://lucene.apache.org/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

⁴ Ounis, Iadh, et al. "Terrier: A High Performance and Scalable Information Retrieval Platform". *Proceedings of ACM SIGIR'06 Workshop on Open Source Information Retrieval (OSIR 2006)*. 2006.

⁵ Mallia, Antonio, et al. "PISA: Performant Indexes and Search for Academia". *Proceedings of the Open-Source IR Replicability Challenge co-located with 42nd International {ACM} {SIGIR} Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval, OSIRRC@SIGIR 2019, Paris, France, July 25, 2019*. 2019.

1.2. Vision for the OpenWebSearch Engine Hub

To define downstream search engines using the OWI, we will also introduce the Open Web Search Engine Hub (OWSE-Hub). Similar to the OWI, the OWSE-Hub forms a web-based information system comparable to the Docker hub, but it will contain complete search engine stacks to enable the fast and easy creation of new search verticals. The architecture of the envisioned OWSE-Hub is outlined in Figure 2.

Figure 2: General architecture of the OWSE-Hub, and how the (federated) search strategy would capture declaratively the usage of indexes retrieved through specifications in the OWSE-Hub. Users can (1-3) pull search engine stacks, (4) build their own specifications for a (composite) search engine, and (5) push specifications to share with others.

Using the OWSE-Hub, users can declaratively define their own search configurations. Users can “pull” pre-defined specifications from the OWSE-Hub, use those to “build” their own custom search engines, and “push” the most useful ones to share these with others. This flexible setup allows for the creation of a wide variety of search engines, not only for commercial usage but also for personal and corporate search, and allowing both centralized and federated search setups.

1.3. Legal and ethical considerations

Crawling the Web and creating and sharing our indexes online is bound by legal and ethical constraints. A more complete understanding of these aspects is the topic of a separate deliverable, D6.2: “ELSA-Catalogue & Code of Conduct for Open Web Search”.

For the indexing pipeline discussed here, four aspects in particular need technical support:

1. Security and access control: users must login before they can download our Web indexes, so we can limit access to the data and restrict possible usage.
2. Take-down requests: we need to remove items from stored data and indexes, manage a *changelog*, and legally enforce index users to track it and apply its updates.
3. Transparency: ensure that the provision of data adheres to the content owner’s expression of intended use (e.g., comply with `robots.txt` and Gen-AI or no-index flags).
4. Harmful/ problematic content: develop and apply preprocessing techniques to identify and annotate problematic content (e.g., add trigger warnings, label information quality).

Enforcing compliance with updates to the index after download is foreseen in the Open Web Index license, where the access control mechanisms implemented ensure that users agree with this license before they can use the data.

We yet have to develop the mechanism to expire and replace or to modify indexes with pending updates; this is taken up in the final year of the project. Apart from invalidating the inverted files with pending updates, we should also develop a standardized method to blacklist sets of document identifiers and filter out invalidated results during retrieval.

Furthermore, work package 6 plans to develop an instrument for *ethical self-assessment*, that we will make mandatory before enabling downloads. The self-assessments will be made transparent for the community, so people can check (public) services that use the OWI against the commitments made during self-assessment; another route to reduce risks and limit inappropriate usage of data we provide.

Finally, we apply the labeling of problematic content during crawling and pre-processing, with a best-effort commitment (as no automatic method will ever be fault-free). The resulting annotations are shared through the index metadata.

2. The Open Web Index

For the first years, our main priority for the OWI was to develop and deploy a full pipeline that crawls (a part of) the Web, pre-processes and indexes the web content, and makes the resulting indexes available in shared storage.

2.1 Overview

We define the architecture for the full pipeline in terms of *cluster tiers*. A cluster tier is defined as a *well-defined set of services* (and corresponding software-stack) that *must* run in the same cluster / set of virtual machines. Figure 3 outlines a first version for cluster tiers and their interplay.

Figure 3: Cluster tiers in the core architecture behind the OWI. A cluster tier is defined as a set of machines running a well-defined software stack in the same physical data-center for a particular purpose with clear, well defined interfaces to other cluster tiers

We describe the different cluster tiers in more detail below.

2.2 Crawling (WP 1)

Crawling takes place on the following two cluster tiers:

- The Crawling Cluster Tier (CCT) contains a crawler responsible for crawling the Web, thereby creating WARC files (i.e., collections of HTTP streams from the crawling process). These WARC⁶ files are stored in an S3 bucket⁷ that can be accessed by the other tiers. There can be multiple CCT, but there should be only one CCT per data center, as the CCT can scale with the amount of resources provided.

⁶ International Organization for Standardization. (2017). *Information and documentation – WARC file format* (ISO/DIS Standard No. 28500). Retrieved from <https://www.iso.org/standard/68004.html> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

⁷ Amazon AWS S3. Available: <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

- The Crawler Frontier Tier (CFT) is a singleton tier (i.e., only one instance exists across all participating data centers). It coordinates the multi-tier crawling process, keeping track of crawled URLs, access statistics and cache digest. The crawler frontier is the primary data source for the website registry, which provides the interface for interaction between webmasters and the frontier (e.g., an interface for take-down requests).

The CCT consists of the OWLer (OWS.eu crawler), a distributed web crawler built with StormCrawler⁸ running on Apache Storm, at each individual data center. Aside from regular crawling functionality, the OWLer also includes a classifier for distinguishing between benign, malicious and adult content.

The CFT consists of a single OpenSearch⁹ instance running at one of the data centers. It also contains a metrics server which aggregates logs from different stages and allows for (limited) statistical analysis.

Currently (September 2024), the CCT has been deployed successfully at five partner sites (UNI PASSAU, BADW-LRZ, IT4I@VSB, CSC and DLR) and is in operation at three (BADW-LRZ, IT4I@VSB and CSC). The CFT is deployed at CERN. At peak operating time, the CCT crawls roughly 1TB of content per day per data center, but can theoretically be scaled up by using more machines. This requires also to resolve security related issues, like raising false positive network security alarms when accessing botnets. However, the frontier still remains a bottleneck to be scaled up accordingly with the number of machines used.

2.3 Preprocessing and content analysis (WP 2)

Preprocessing and content analysis encompasses the following two cluster tiers:

- The Preprocessing and Enrichment Tier (PET) takes the WARC files from the S3 Bucket filled by the CCT and extracts cleaned HTML and metadata. The extracted metadata includes the page's language, several properties derived from the URL, and Curlie¹⁰ topics. Later on, other metadata such as geo-information and entities will also be extracted. Following the partitioning of the CCT, each data center should have a dedicated PET for the WARC files stored at that data center. The metadata extracted by the PET is stored in Parquet format.
- The Preprocessing Plugins Evaluation Tier (PPET) is another singleton tier that enables the evaluation of plugins for the content analysis library. In order to expand enrichment capabilities, both project members as well as third parties may develop plugins to be used in the PET.

To ensure good quality and sufficient throughput, candidate plugins first have to perform their enrichment task on problem-specific benchmarking data (e.g., a classification dataset for a plugin performing webpage classification), using an instance of the TIRA¹¹ platform hosted at one of the data centers. This platform provides the means for evaluation as a service with a focus on information retrieval research. It can host shared tasks on a given research problem, run submitted software in virtual machines and thereby create reproducible results.

⁸ DigitalPebble, Ltd. (2014). StormCrawler, <https://stormcrawler.apache.org/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

⁹ Amazon Web Services (2021). OpenSearch, <https://opensearch.org/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

¹⁰ Curlie. Available: <https://curlie.org/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

¹¹ Fröbe, Maik, et al. "Continuous integration for reproducible shared tasks with TIRA.io." *European Conference on Information Retrieval*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2023.

The PET uses Apache Spark batch jobs that apply Resiliparse¹² to parse and clean the HTML content and apply several types of metadata enrichment. The work on this tier is outlined in further detail in Deliverable D2.1.

The PET runs currently (September 2024) at the same infrastructure sites as the CCT (BADW-LRZ, IT4I@VSB and CSC). Functionality is in place to estimate the amount of resources required for processing a day's worth of WARC files, such that the PET can scale along with the amount of content being crawled by the CCT.

The PPET builds upon TIRA, a platform for replicability and comparison of information retrieval experiments. Currently, TIRA is hosted at WEBIS and is being used for the evaluation of several shared tasks at well-known IR conferences. We are looking into hosting a TIRA instance at one of the infrastructure partners, to serve as the core part of the PPET to evaluate PET plugins.

2.4 Indexing (WP 3)

Indexing is supported in the Index and Storage Tier (IST).

The IST turns the cleaned content from the PET into a usable index/inverted file. Similar to the CCT and the PET, each data center should have its own IST (and only one), responsible for creating an index for the documents crawled by that data center. Indexes are inverted files partitioned into so-called "shards" by selected types of metadata derived by the PET (e.g., topic and language), distributed as CIFF¹³ files.

Similar to the PET, the IST is implemented as a Spark batch job. In its current state, it reads the Parquet files delivered by the PET and writes out inverted files per shard (by arbitrary metadata values). This allows us to build semantically coherent shards of the full web index (dependent on the metadata extracted by the PET), which can be used to enable a large variety of downstream search engines. For instance, language can be used to build search engines for specific countries, geo-information can be used to focus on specific areas, and classified topics or genres can be used to build search engines focusing on a specific area (like news and/or sports).

Aside from creating the CIFF files per shard, the IST also copies the Parquet files written by the PET and partitions them alongside the CIFF files. The Parquet files are distributed alongside the CIFF files and can be used to enrich the index with the appropriate metadata.

Currently (September, 2024) the IST has successfully been deployed to BADW-LRZ, IT4I@VSB and CSC. Current efforts are focusing on more robust deployment of the PET and IST and making this process more automated. Future work in this task needs to resolve the questions that arise from a fully evolving index; for example, how and if CIFF files should be updated in response to changing document content and/or take-down requests.

2.5 Infrastructure (WP 5)

At the time of writing (September 2024), the full technology stack behind the OWI has been deployed at BADW-LRZ, IT4I@VSB and CSC, with plans to onboard the new data centers that join the project through FSTP #3. The CFT and corresponding metrics services run at CERN. The different services are currently secured via IP address and thus not accessible from outside the participating services / VPN connections to the computing centers.

¹² Bevendorff, Janek, et al. "Elastic chatnoir: Search engine for the clueweb and the common crawl." *Advances in Information Retrieval: 40th European Conference on IR Research, ECIR 2018, Grenoble, France, March 26-29, 2018, Proceedings 40*. Springer International Publishing, 2018.

¹³ Lin, Jimmy, et al. "Supporting Interoperability Between Open-Source Search Engines with the Common Index File Format". *Proceedings of the 43rd International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*. 2020.

A core contribution to this successful deployment is the development of a consistent data infrastructure across all data centers. The data infrastructure is built with iRODS¹⁴, allowing for seamless federated access to the data at each of the data centers. On top of the iRODS layer, each data center runs Minio¹⁵ or an S3-compliant storage to provide a uniform S3-like access point to the OWS crawl data.

Initially, all data was transferred in between the infrastructure tiers by writing to and reading from S3 buckets in this federated data architecture. However, to improve throughput and reduce the load on the S3 instances, we adopted a new approach in which the PET and IST run together in a single HPC workflow within the LEXIS platform¹⁶. The PET still reads the WARC files from S3, but stores the output Parquet files in temporary scratch space at the local data center. The IST then reads from this temporary storage and creates the output index shards. Daily index slices are published as LEXIS Datasets on top of the federated iRODS infrastructure. This combined workflow has successfully been deployed at IT4I@VSB and CSC, with ongoing work also focusing on getting it set up properly at BADW-LRZ.

While the pipeline can be run properly at three of the infrastructure partners, the integration of the pipeline into the LEXIS platform – which is essential for cross-data workflow execution and data management - has proven to be difficult. We have run into a number of issues during this deployment, that need to be resolved before we can extend and improve the workflows (e.g. by adding new datasets to be created or automatically running the workflows). As a result, the preprocessing and indexing has been lagging behind the crawler, and only data until March/April 2024 has been released as public index datasets. Our number one priority for next year is to have the workflows running steadily so we can keep up with the crawlers and ensure that we process updates to the index (including take-down requests).

2.6 The actual Open Web Index

The final product of the full pipeline described above – the Open Web Index – consists of all public datasets produced by the federated datastructure and published through LEXIS (see also Figure 1). Each dataset contains CIFF and Parquet files, partitioned across language. Access control to LEXIS (and thus, the OWI) is arranged through B2ACCESS¹⁷.

To use the Open Web Index, downstream search engines would download the CIFF files they are interested in (e.g. with a specific language or from a specific date range), and import them into a search engine of their choice.¹⁸ Alongside the CIFF files, the metadata Parquet files can be downloaded for additional use in a search engine. For instance, the cleaned text can be used for snippet extraction, and the metadata fields can be used to enrich or filter the search results obtained by a full-text search on the index.

The Open Web Index is provided as daily shards per data-center form of so-called data sets. A data set follows a particular folder structure, as depicted in the image on the right and has associated metadata containing elements of the Data Cite vocabulary¹⁹ and application-specific metadata,

```
OWI Dataset
- Year=2023
- month=12

- day=24

-language=eng

index.ciff.gz
metadata_#.parquet

-language=....

- changelog.json
```

¹⁴ iRODS Consortium. iRODS, <https://irods.org/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

¹⁵ MinIO, Inc (2016). MinIO, <https://min.io/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

¹⁶ LEXIS Platform, <https://lexis-project.eu/web/lexis-platform/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

¹⁷ B2ACCESS, <https://www.eudat.eu/catalogue/b2access> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

¹⁸ Section 2.7 describes the newly developed `owilix` command line tool to access to the OWI in detail.

¹⁹ <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

particularly start data, end date and collection name. The `changelog.json` file contains potential changes to an index partition, like items removed due to take down requests.

2.7 Access to the Open Web Index

Datasets are available for download via the LEXIS Portal (preferably using the `owilix CLI`²⁰), which serves as central access point for data artifacts and HPC workflows. Users can get access to the portal via authentication using B2ACCESS - a European wide identity provider platform from EUDAT.eu. The portal contains a download section (see Figure 4) for public and project-private datasets. Public thereby denotes that every authenticated user can download the dataset. Project-private denotes that users must be member of the OpenWebSearch.eu project for being able to download the data. Project-private datasets are used to store and share the raw crawl data, which requires tighter access control due to legal reasons.

Data download via the LEXIS Web Portal is limited for three reasons:

1. The LEXIS Portal is a general purpose platform for HPC workflows and does not offer OWS specific functionality;
2. Downloading data from the LEXIS platform would require that all data is streamed from a single data center, which is inefficient;
3. A web UI does not allow proper automation and can only provide limited tooling.

Consequently, we have developed the Open Web Index Command Line Tool, also known as `owilix`, to improve accessibility to the Open Web index. `owilix` is a sophisticated command-line interface tool designed to manage data slices for the Open Web Index (OpenWebIndex.eu). `owilix` offers pull as well as push functionality and integrates powerful SQL querying capabilities via DuckDB and the Parquet file format. While pull functionality allows for downloading the OWI-shards, push is designed to accept community contributions, like for example dense index files or additional metadata. This tool is essential for researchers, developers, and data scientists working with large-scale web datasets, providing efficient means to version, retrieve, manage, and analyze data from the Open Web Index ecosystem.

`owilix` stands out in its ability to handle both local and remote datasets, offering a seamless experience in data management across different environments. Its primary purpose is to facilitate operations such as pulling data, listing files with specific criteria, and executing complex queries on datasets, making it an indispensable asset for anyone working with web-scale data in the context of open web search initiatives.

²⁰ <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owi-cli/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

Figure 4 Screenshot of the LEXIS Portal Download Area

1.1.1 Architecture

The architecture of owilix is designed to integrate smoothly with the broader Open Web Index ecosystem while providing a standalone utility for data management and querying. Figure 5 shows the core elements of owilix. The tool is written in python and built on py4lexis, the Python interface for the LEXIS Platform. It interacts with the LEXIS Platform for logging (via B2ACCESS / EUDAT services) and for getting dataset metadata. Pulling and pushing datasets happens directly via iRODS, which offers efficient parallel download capabilities. On top of iRODS we are using DuckDB as SQL querying engine, which allows for efficient, remote and parallel querying of index partitions stored in iRODS.

Figure 5: core elements of owilix

Here's an overview of its key architectural components and relationships:

1. Core CLI Interface:

The heart of owilix is its command-line interface, which interprets user commands and orchestrates actions across other components. This interface is built using Python, ensuring cross-platform compatibility and ease of extension.

2. **Local Data Manager:**
This component handles operations on local datasets, including insertion, listing, and statistical analysis. It manages the local storage of datasets, typically in a designated directory (defaulting to `$HOME/.owi`).
3. **Remote Data Interface:**
Responsible for interactions with remote data centers, this component facilitates operations like pulling datasets and comparing versions across different remote locations.
4. **Data Versioning System:**
Drawing parallels to Git, `owilix` implements a versioning system for datasets. This allows users to push local changes to remote repositories and pull updates from remote sources, maintaining a history of dataset versions.
5. **Query Engine Integration:**
The `owilix` CLI seamlessly integrates with DuckDB, a powerful *embedded* analytical database system. This integration enables complex querying capabilities directly on Parquet files, both locally and remotely.
6. **Authentication Module:**
Ensures secure access to remote resources by managing user authentication, typically through token-based systems.
7. **Plugin System:**
Allows for the extension of `owilix`'s capabilities through additional modules, such as specific repository types or custom query engines.

Relationships with other Components:

- **Open Web Index Infrastructure:** `owilix` is designed to work with the broader OWI infrastructure, including various data centers and the central OWI repository.
- **Data Centers:** The tool interacts directly with different data centers (e.g., LRZ, IT4I, CSC) for remote operations.
- **MOSAIC:** Primary client tool for using the OWI index; more detail in Section 3.2 below.
- **DuckDB:** Tight integration with DuckDB enables powerful querying capabilities directly on dataset files.
- **iRODS:** Utilizes iRODS for efficient file system operations, especially in remote data handling.

1.1.2 Common Use Cases and Example Commands

The OWI CLI tool is versatile and can be used in various scenarios, reflecting the needs of different users within the OpenWebSearch.eu ecosystem:

1. **Querying Data:** Users can retrieve specific datasets or records from OpenSearch by specifying criteria such as date ranges, data centers, or metadata tags.
2. **Managing Datasets:** The CLI allows users to manage their datasets effectively. This includes inserting new datasets, listing available datasets, and deleting outdated records. Users can also perform statistical analyses on their datasets, providing insights into the structure and content of the data they are working with.
3. **Troubleshooting and Debugging:** In cases where issues arise within the aggregation pipeline, the CLI can be used to diagnose and resolve problems. Users can query logs,

check the status of the pipeline, or inspect specific data flows to identify and address any issues

Practical examples of how the OWI CLI commands are used:

- **Listing Local Datasets:** A user can run the command `owilix local ls all:latest` to list all the datasets available locally that were indexed on the latest date. The output would include a summary of the datasets, including metadata such as the date of indexing, the data center source, and the dataset size.
- **Pulling Data from Remote Servers:** To pull data from a remote data center, a user could issue the command `owilix remote pull lrz:latest/access=public`. This would download the latest public datasets from the LRZ data center, storing them locally for further analysis.
- **Advanced Querying:** A more complex command might involve querying specific data records, such as `owilix query less --remote all:2023-12-4 limit=500 "where=url_suffix='at'"`. This command would retrieve records from December 4, 2023, filtering for URLs with suffix “at”, limiting the results to 500 entries.

1.1.3 Source Code and Documentation

More information can be found under the following links:

- Source Code: <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owi-cli>;
- Tutorial on using owilix: https://openwebsearcheu-public.pages.it4i.eu/ows-the-book/content/howto/data_download_with_owilix.html;
- Tutorial on data slicing with owilix: https://openwebsearcheu-public.pages.it4i.eu/ows-the-book/content/howto/data_slicing_with_owilix.html.

3. The OpenWebSearch Engine Hub

In the first year of the project, the main focus has been put on developing and deploying a first version of the Open Web Index. As a result, development on the OWSE-Hub had not yet started (in line with the schedule of the project). Nevertheless, first steps towards building the OWSE-Hub had been taken, by integrating the indexer (the IST) and the CIFF standard into TIRA. This has given us a first glimpse into how we can use the indexes constructed by the IST in a centralized platform, helpful to make our vision for the OWSE-Hub more concrete.

In the second year, an initial implementation of an OpenWebSearch Engine Hub (OWSE-Hub) has been developed that follows the vision of the OWSE-Hub as outlined in Section 1.2. This software, called MOSAIC2go, is not a full implementation of the OWSE-Hub and provides a limited set of features, nevertheless it tests and demonstrates the overall vision. MOSAIC2go enables users to create and configure a search engine that uses datasets downloaded from the Open Web Index (see Section 2.7). The produced search engine is a MOSAIC instance, that includes the selected OWI data sets in its search index and provides an interface to search in this index. More information on MOSAIC can be found in D4.1.

3.1 Overall concept and system architecture

MOSAIC2go aims to simplify the process of creating an own search engine or search application by providing an assembly mechanism. Potential search engine operators and end users can utilize MOSAIC2go to build a customized and configured MOSAIC instance. Customized and configured instances are available for 24 hours and can be directly downloaded or shared via a download link. Users of MOSAIC2go can select from a list of available index partitions from the OWI. These selected partitions are then included in the downloadable MOSAIC instance. In addition, users can specify MOSAIC related configurations such as modules that should be included and a personalized web interface.

The back-end of MOSAIC2go's system architecture is developed using Python and FastAPI²¹, which together provides the configuration service. This subsystem is responsible for processing user requests related to the selection of index partitions and modules, as well as managing various configurations related to the web interface and search engine settings (see Figure 6). Upon receiving a request through the provided REST API, the configuration service will package the index partitions and MOSAIC with its configurations either to a .zip file or to a Dockerfile. A download link is then sent back to the user via the API. The front-end of MOSAIC2go delivers a user-friendly visual editor for configuring the MOSAIC search engine instance. This visual editor allows users to select index partitions, modules, and other configurations through a web interface. The front-end communicates with the back-end service via the REST API to submit user selections and receive the configured .zip file or Dockerfile.

3.2 Usage

To provide index partitions to users, MOSAIC2go supports two different application modes. If enabled, the "online" mode of MOSAIC2go can use the information of particular index partitions specified in a JSON file. The entries in the JSON file include metadata of the index partition such as the name, an optional short description, the number of indexed documents and a URL where the index partition can be downloaded. The information from this JSON file is then used to expose the available index partitions to the users via the REST API and to download and include selected index partitions in the configured MOSAIC instance.

²¹ Sebastián Ramírez (2018). FastAPI, <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

MOSAIC2go’s “offline” mode uses index partitions that are stored in the local file system of the device on which the application is running. By default, the index partitions stored in `$HOME/.owi/public` and `$HOME/.owi/localpipeline` are exposed via the API and can be selected for configurations since this is the default local storage for index partitions downloaded with `owilix` (see Section 2.7). However, these paths are configurable, thus custom index partitions can be offered to users.

Users can utilize MOSAIC2go to configure their custom MOSAIC instance by either using the web interface (see Figure 7) or directly sending an HTTP GET request with the desired parameters to the REST API and then downloading it using the URL in the response.

The downloaded .zip file of a configured MOSAIC instance contains the source code of the respective customized MOSAIC instance together with selected index partitions. The customized MOSAIC instance can then be started using the provided scripts or by creating a Docker container utilizing the Dockerfile shipped in the archive file.

Figure 6: Concept and simplified system architecture of MOSAIC2go

MOSAIC2go

Welcome to the OpenWebSearch.eu MOSAIC2go configurator! Customize your personalised search engine based on the MOSAIC framework step by step based on your preferences.

Step 1: Select Index(es)

Choose one or multiple indices that should be served by your search engine. It is not required to select one of the provided indices since you can create your own index or download an existing index using [OWIer](#) at a later date.

<input type="checkbox"/> Simple Wiki	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unis Graz	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unis Austria
<input type="checkbox"/> DLR Prototype	<input type="checkbox"/> DLR Prototype Extended	<input type="checkbox"/> OWI Snapshot

Step 2: Select Modules

Choose one or multiple metadata modules that should be included in your personal search engine.

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Core (Required)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Shared (Required)	<input type="checkbox"/> Geo
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Keywords		

Step 3: Customize the Web User Interface

Select your own title and a color for the surrounding area of the title.

Title

Surrounding Color

Step 4: Set Search Engine URL

Set the base URL of your search engine if you already know the URL that will expose the search service.

Base URL

[Download as archive file](#) [Download Dockerfile](#)

Generated Search Engines

The following search engines have been generated. You can download the archive file for each search engine instance. The instances will be available for 24 hours.

[mosaic_q0dBQImWje.zip](#) [Download as archive file](#)

OpenWebSearch.eu

The project OpenWebSearch.EU has received funding from the European Union's Horizon research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101070014.

Figure 7: Web Interface of MOSAIC2go

3.3. Ethical and legal implications

Downloading and using the data sets and index files from the OWI has legal and ethical implications (see D6.2). The usage of index files is regulated by the Open Web Index License

(OWIL)²² which provides a legal framework for dealing with this data. Furthermore, index users also need to accept ethical standards when making use of the downloaded index files.

Considering these ethical and legal implications, a design decision has been made that users always have to download the index files from the OWSE Hub, before they can be used to search the Web (also see Section 2.7). The resulting separation of concerns ensures that users explicitly take ethical and legal responsibility for using and managing their search engine (with data from the OWI). In contrast, an online platform that would deliver both index files and search engine as a bundle, would need further investigation to deal with ethical and legal requirements.

3.4. Installation and software packages

The configuration service of MOSAIC2go can be installed on any device that supports Python. After installing the requirements, the back-end is ready to be started by serving it using a Python web server implementation (e.g., uvicorn) or by integrating it to a service. Upon starting the back-end application, several REST API endpoints are exposed via the port specified at application start up. The configuration service is intended to be used both locally and on a web server.

MOSAIC2go's front-end for visually configuring MOSAIC instances is implemented using Next.js. Therefore, the front-end application can be started using one of the provided node scripts or by exporting the application to a static build.

More information about the software, installation instructions and download links can be found in the links provided Section 4.1.

²² Farzana, Sheikh Mastura, et al. "Report on the 1st International Workshop on Open Web Search (WOWS 2024) at ECIR 2024." *ACM SIGIR Forum*. Vol. 58. No. 1. ACM, 2024.

4. Outputs and Statistics

4.1. Overview of open-source software outputs

Each of the software components and tools we developed Table 1 lists all of these with links to their respective Git repositories, as well as a version archived on Zenodo.

Table 1: Open-source software packages developed to build and use the OWI and OWSE-HUB.

Title	Open Web Search Crawler (OWLer) StormCrawler (see also D1.1)
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owler
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278932

Title	Open Web Search Crawler (OWLer) URLFrontier (see also D1.1)
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/urlfrontier
Archived	https://zenodo.org/records/13837305

Title	Resiliparse: WARC/HTML parsing and preprocessing library
Repository	https://github.com/chatnoir-eu/chatnoir-resiliparse
Archived	https://zenodo.org/records/13739396

Title	Resilipipe: Preprocessing at scale
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/preprocessing-pipeline
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13784624

Title	TIRA: platform for replicability and comparison of IR experiments
Repository	https://github.com/tira-io/tira
Archived	https://zenodo.org/records/13739358

Title	Open Web Search Indexer
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/spark-indexer
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8261098

Title	Spark deployment framework
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/spark-deployment
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13693137

Title	CIFF toolkit: library for processing WARC files
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/ciff-toolkit/
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13693064

Title	CIFF to Lucene index converter
Repository	https://github.com/informagi/lucene-ciff
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13710610

Title	Owilix: a command line tool for access to the OWI
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owi-cli
Archived	https://zenodo.org/records/13833664

Title	MOSAIC2go Configuration Tool
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu/wp4/mosaic2go-configuration-service https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu/wp4/mosaic2go-web-frontend <i>Private and password protected repositories</i>
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13800054

4.2 Statistics of the Open Web Index

Table 2 shows some statistics of the OWI, measured at the end of August 2024, as an overview of the amount of data we have been able to process towards the end of the second year. More statistics can be found on the OWLer Dashboard²³.

Table 2: Statistics of the OWI, as measured on August 31st 2024.

Documents crawled	Up to ~105M / day
Documents preprocessed + indexed	~ 2.2B
Number of public daily index datasets	198
Number of unique languages	600+
Number of unique domains	40,531,574 until 6th of May 2024

4.3 Top domains crawled

Table 3 shows the top domains crawled in the time between October 2023 and July 202.

Table 3: Top domains crawled in the time between October 2023 and July 2024.

Domain	Fraction	Absolute Count
blogspot.com	26.46%	5,563,708
wordpress.com	12.12%	2,549,134
wikipedia.org	9.55%	2,007,679
fc2.com	4.27%	897,966
hatenablog.com	3.31%	696,717
europa.eu	2.67%	561,532
free.fr	2.57%	539,715
yahoo.com	2.45%	516,114
web.app	1.78%	374,451
altervista.org	1.33%	280,728
medium.com	1.30%	273,705
nih.gov	1.17%	246,284
amazonaws.com	1.13%	238,429
google.com	1.04%	218,500
netlify.app	0.94%	198,200
mit.edu	0.87%	183,035
cloudfront.net	0.81%	170,450
harvard.edu	0.81%	169,597
cocolog-nifty.com	0.75%	158,705
stackexchange.com	0.72%	150,372
uk.com	0.71%	148,608
spb.ru	0.68%	143,962
sakura.ne.jp	0.66%	138,732
wikidot.com	0.63%	131,904
nasa.gov	0.60%	125,834
mpg.de	0.58%	121,058
appspot.com	0.57%	119,594
microsoft.com	0.55%	115,341
us.com	0.55%	114,770
<i>etc.</i>		

²³ <https://dashboard.ows.eu/owler> (Last accessed, September 24th, 2024).

5. Conclusion and Outlook

In this document, we have summarized our work on setting up the Open Web Index in the first two years of the project OpenWebSearch.EU. We have managed to build a full pipeline — from crawling the Web to preprocessing and indexing — that has been deployed at multiple infrastructure partners. At the end of August 2024, over 2 billion webpages have successfully been indexed.

For year 3 of the project, we will focus on higher robustness and better automation of the current workflows. For instance, we wish to have the current LEXIS workflows for preprocessing and indexing running steadily each day, without the need for manual intervention. We will investigate how to best implement the recommendations from WP6, especially with regards to developing a mechanism to update the OWI to respond to take-down requests. We will also extend deployment of the full pipeline to the new infrastructure partners that we onboard as part of FSTP call #3.

Another focus point lies with adoption of the OWI and ease-of-use for users of our data. We aim to work together with the application partners from FSTP call #2 to locate issues with our current data distribution methods and streamline the process of downloading and using the index data.

Finally, we briefly discuss specific plans for each of the cluster tiers below.

5.1 Crawling

In year two (Y2), we plan to improve our web crawler system as follows. First, we want to boost the Crawling Cluster Tier (CCT) by adding more machines, so it can gather between 5 to 10 TB of data daily. Next, we will make it easier for other crawlers to connect with our URL Frontier, allowing them to share their web data in WARC files along with our own crawled data. We also plan to add new features to our crawler, so it can focus on specific topics when collecting data. Lastly, we will improve the efficiency of the URL Frontier to ensure everything runs smoothly and scales up easily.

Beyond the development of the crawler itself, our focus will be on legally compliant crawling. This includes the development of the open webmaster console as well as defining metadata standards for expressing privacy and copyright issues, and filling those from terms of use and privacy statements of websites using machine learning.

5.2 Preprocessing and content analysis

The activities in T5.2 have focused primarily on implementing the PET, and on deploying it with the infrastructure partners. These deployment activities are ongoing, in the form of setting up the LEXIS workflows for automated preprocessing and indexing.

Our goal for the remainder of the project is to extend the capabilities of the PET, by adding new content analysis modules to Resilipipe. As outlined in D2.1 “The OpenWebSearch WARC parsing & content analysis library”, we provide a standardized interface for the implementation of content analysis modules. This enables both members of the project as well as third parties to implement new content analyzers, while ensuring sufficient standardization in the creation of modules. Specific activities for extending the PET with new content analysis modules are described in Deliverable 2.3 “Semantic Enrichment Algorithms and Models”.

5.3 Indexing

Our main priority for indexing (combined with preprocessing and content analysis) for the coming time is to make sure the workflows are up and running correctly, without the need for manual action. On top of that, we have previously worked towards the creation of “collection indices”: sets of filters that can create custom subsets or index shards from the OWI data. We will incorporate

the creation of collection indices into the existing pipelines, so these are also created automatically.

We will again continue to work together with WP4 and (especially) the newly onboarded partners through FSTP call #2 to ensure usage of the OWI is simple and effective for users of our data.

Research-wise, we will continue our work on the evaluation and improvement of semantic sharding for fine-grained, individual use of certain shards from the OWI. We also investigate whether index shards in object storage (e.g. S3 or iRODS) could be queried directly, to allow for an alternative way of using the OWI in which queries can be processed (albeit with lower efficiency) without downloading large index files first.

5.4 OWSE-Hub

With MOSAIC2go as a first implementation of (part of) our vision for the OWSE-Hub, we will extend this concept in the next year. During the Workshop on Open Web Search (WOWS 2024), we discussed what search specifications in the OWSE-Hub should look like²⁴: detailing at least a choice of *backend*, *frontend*, a *document collection or index files*, and possibly some *middleware*. MOSAIC2go now implements this choice of index files, frontend and middleware for one specific backend (search engine). We will determine what format to use for the search engine specifications and implement at least one additional backend for which search engines can easily be created through the OWSE-Hub.

²⁴ <https://openwebsearch.eu/owil-current/> (Last accessed: September 24th, 2024).